

Understanding Urban Form - Hierarchical Morphotope Classification based on Gradually Loosening Spatial Restrictions

Martin Fleischmann*¹ and Krasen Samardzhiev^{†1}

¹Charles University, Albertov 6, 128 00 Prague, CZ

GISRUK 2025

Summary

The physical structure of cities is under-studied due to data, methodological and theoretical limitations. We propose the hierarchical morphotope classification (HiMoC) - a scalable, hierarchical method for classifying urban form based on the concept of morphotopes — morphologically homogeneous areas. Using a bottom-up approach, it combines morphometric analysis with a bespoke clustering method called Gradually Loosening Spatial Restrictions (GLSR) to delineate and classify urban patterns into a taxonomic tree. We apply the method to 90 million buildings across six countries, to create a detailed, hierarchical urban typology while maintaining adaptability for various use cases. The taxonomy extends traditional classifications, offering deeper insights into urban structures and fostering reproducibility through open data and code.

KEYWORDS: urban form, classification, taxonomy, morphology

1 Introduction

Whenever we look at a city we cannot escape its physical form. The way buildings are laid out, the patterns of streets, the unique open spaces and transformations we observe when we move between neighbourhoods are among the strongest impressions a city leaves. Yet, when looking at the ways science deals with this particular aspect of primary human habitat, there's still a lot we don't know. One of the reasons is the complexity urban form encapsulates. The patterns of form are rich, complex and complicated. Researchers use methods like classification to reduce this complexity into well-defined types. The contribution described in this paper aims to provide a quantitative method of a classification of urban form that avoids oversimplification while preserving interpretability and scalability.

Urban form has been studied in many ways, from the traditional, primarily qualitative, schools of urban morphology (Oliveira, 2016), to continental (European Environment Agency & European

*martin.fleischmann@natur.cuni.cz

†krasen.samardzhiev@natur.cuni.cz

Environment Agency, 2020) or even global data products (Demuzere et al., 2022; Dijkstra et al., 2021). However, the larger the scale, the simpler the set of classes. For example, the Copernicus Urban Atlas (European Environment Agency & European Environment Agency, 2020) is a simple combination of continuity, density and land use, while the urban classes of Local Climate Zones (Stewart & Oke, 2012) are derived from compactness, height and land cover. Degree of Urbanisation (Dijkstra et al., 2021) is even simpler, based on pure density. While all of these have their use cases, we need to look for method more closer to original urban morphology to highlight patterns of intra-urban development.

While urban morphology is still predominantly a qualitative field, it is slowly incorporating quantitative methods, primarily through urban morphometrics. Urban morphometrics is defined as a “*a study of urban form through the means of quantitative assessment of its constituent elements*” and is based on a set of measurements of buildings, streets and similar features, capturing the layout they form. While the idea of morphometrics goes back to the work of MRG (1988), it only recently started to grow, with the works of Araldi and Fusco (2019, 2024), Bobkova et al. (2019), or that of Fleischmann et al. (2022). What these new methods of urban form analysis have in common is the bottom-up approach - the analysis is done on the level of individual elements of urban form and only then generalised to assess the patterns. Nevertheless, no current quantitative method is at the same time scalable, detailed, adaptive and potentially extensible.

This paper presents one method that aims to fulfil all these needs - *hierarchical morphotope classification (HiMoC)* - a scalable hierarchical classification of physical structure of cities, towns and other settlements derived from the idea of a morphotope as the smallest morphologically homogeneous piece of land. It is scalable, as it can grow to tens of millions of buildings (and possibly more), detailed, as it classifies every single building in the area, adaptive to the use case due to its hierarchical nature and extensible, as the additional areas just expand the existing taxonomic tree.

2 Methods

In the core of the method lies the idea of a morphotope, defined by Conzen (1975, p. 259) and reported by Larkham and Jones (1991) as “*the smallest urban locality obtaining distinctive character among their neighbours from their particular combination of constituent morphological elements.*” The method hence first delineates morphotopes based on morphometric characteristics of individual elements and then builds the similarity matrix between morphotopes, resulting in a hierarchical classification in the form of a taxonomic tree.

2.1 Morphometrics

The method starts with the morphometric characterisation of building footprints derived from the approach proposed by Arribas-Bel and Fleischmann (2022), making use of the enclosed tessellation as the algorithmically generated aerial unit capturing the land belonging to each building and the spatial contiguity relations between features. In total we measure 59 morphometric characters capturing all the aspects of urban form from individual dimensions and shapes to spatial distribution, intensity and diversity to street network connectivity, using the Python package `momepy`

(Fleischmann, 2019), that has been completely rewritten to provide necessary performance.

2.2 GLSR classification

With that, we apply a bespoke method of hierarchical classification based on gradually loosening spatial restrictions (GLSR). The GLSR classification uses three steps - the first one to delineate morphotopes, the second to organise them into regional typology and the third to generate top-level taxonomic tree. In the first step, we use agglomerative clustering based on spatially constrained Ward’s tree and the “*leaf*” cluster extraction method, described in McInnes et al. (2017) to extract flat clusters, where each represents a morphotope. This step has a strict spatial restriction resulting in regionalisation with a high number of clusters. The second step applies agglomerative clustering on top of morphotopes within a morphologically continuous region - a portion of land where the nearest neighbour is at maximum 500 meters away - to generate baseline morphotope types. While there is no spatial restriction within the algorithm, its application to a single region prioritises local similarities over the global ones resulting in more consistent delineation. The last step takes the baseline types and runs the final divisive clustering, resulting in a single hierarchical tree for the whole study area.

3 Data

The initial version of the morphotope taxonomy is built for 6 countries of Central and Eastern Europe (Germany, Austria, Czechia, Poland, Slovakia, Lithuania), covering over 90 million buildings sourced from national cadastral databases and related street network data sourced from the Overture Maps project. The building layer has been further preprocessed using the `geoplanar` Python package (Rey et al., 2023) to fix topology and planarity issues, while the street network was filtered and reduced to the morphological (centreline) network using the adaptive simplification method developed for the purpose and released in `neatnet` (Fleischmann et al., 2024).

4 Results

The resulting classification is composed of over 600 thousand morphotopes spreading across 867 regions, leading to 64 726 baseline types classified into a single taxonomic tree, with its top layers illustrated in Figure Figure 1. The divisive algorithm results in an organised tree with different *levels* of resolution matching the split iteration level, making it possible to derive classifications at different levels that a researcher or municipality might require.

The tree allows us to identify, for example, classes that correspond to traditional perimeter blocks in cities like Prague, Vienna, and Berlin, while a deeper cut showcases that there are block types typical for Berlin that are present only sporadically in Prague and vice versa. The same could be done for any type of urban development.

The resulting classification is validated using external open data products capturing similar concepts like the Urban Atlas or Local Climate Zones, ensuring that the classes are consistent with the established methods, as well as providing new information.

Figure 1: Classification of a portion of Prague with a taxonomic tree showcasing the uncovered (dis)similarity between baseline types or urban morphotopes.

The results are released as an open data product under permissive license (the exact license depends on the region and the restrictions of the original data provider) together with fully reproducible code available at https://github.com/uscuni/urban_taxonomy.

Acknowledgements

The authors kindly acknowledge funding by the Charles University's Primus programme through the project "Influence of Socioeconomic and Cultural Factors on Urban Structure in Central Europe", project reference PRIMUS/24/SCI/023.

Biographies

Martin Fleischmann is a Research Associate at the Department of Social Geography and Regional Development at the Charles University in Prague. He leads the Research Team on Urban Structure focusing on cities, from their internal structure or interactions to the evolutionary patterns capturing their past and future.

Krasen Samardzhiev is a Postdoctoral Researcher at the Department of Social Geography and Regional Development at the Charles University in Prague within the Research Team on Urban Structure. His interest lies in geographic data science in urban environments, with a focus on morphology of cities.

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